

ISic1212

I.Sicily inscription 1212

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, private house

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140696

1. Ἀδείμαν [τος]

2. [Ἀ]ρι [στ— —]

3.

Edition: PHI334660

1. Ἀδείμαν [τος] ²⁷Ἀδειμάν[του]²⁷

2. [Φ]ρίξι[ου].

3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492816

EDCS 39101576

PHI 140696

PHI 334660

Bibliography

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